

Language Acquisition with the help of ICT

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Abstract

In general, a person's attitude determines how well they acquire a language; if he desires to learn, he will attempt to do so in a variety of methods; as the adage goes, "Practice makes perfect." He attempts to imitate others before attempting to communicate in the same manner with those he is following. He practices on a regular basis. With the assistance of information and communication technology-based resources, virtual classrooms, and social networks, language education is accessible to all. New learners are significantly impacted by network access, which grants them opportunities to interact with others, exchange information, seek clarification, and increase their cognizance in the target language. Nevertheless, the exponential growth of resources and instruments for learning a foreign language or a new one presents both advantages and disadvantages. Understanding the sequence of ICT in language acquisition is of the utmost importance, as it allows for the accommodation of the unique requirements of each learner. In addition, it is critical that the use of ICT and its support be implemented in a sustainable manner across a variety of domains, culminate in clarification and reach a conclusion, while promoting the acquisition of a target language for lifelong learning. Modern web users are increasingly reliant on mobile devices, computers, and laptops; they can utilize a variety of media to communicate and convey themselves. These platforms may consist of traditional blog websites like YouTube and Blogger.com, as well as social networking sites like Twitter, Skype, Telegram, WhatsApp, and Facebook. While these sites still incorporate blog tools, they also promote user self-expression in accordance with their own criteria. Furthermore, the most prominent application of these spoken expressions tools in the context of a target language is in the exploration of the target language or a domain that arises within that context.

Keywords: Language acquisition, Information, Communication, Technology.

INTRODUCTION

Now-a-days, English is one of the most important languages which has played a major role in the process of globalization and knowledge explosion. It is the most common means of communication throughout the globe. English termed as Link Language, Global language as well as Lingua Franca. In Indian context it is treated as EFL (English as a Foreign Language) and ESL (English as a Second Language). We eagerly interested to acquire the English language as much as early with an intension. The use of English language has become vital for better learning and earning with employment. Therefore it is necessary to learn English and develop English language

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skills among the students from the school level. There is a little information on the value placed on language acquiring in the former days, when the people used to learn foreign languages and what they did with their newly acquired language. English motivates, passion and goals must be inferred from the people's behavior and what is known of the overall context. Here one fact immediately stands out: the absence of overt prescriptions.

As many general opinion of the intersection between ICT (Information and Communication Technology) and language learning comes to a close, the discussion turns ever more towards language learning rather than language use, how the nature of language learning have changed along with, or possibly in response to technological progress, that it is easy to acquire and understand the target language, like any other human activity, is subject to the influence of social developments and trends. It makes it possible to discern trends and patterns and reveals insights of relevance to the current situation and to current debates. But most of them are traditional, less interesting, in effective as well as lack of motivation. So it is necessary to use modern approaches and tools of ICT to develop better understanding and acquisition of basic skills like L-S-R-W (Listening-Speaking-Reading-Writing) of English language among the students at different levels and the people in the society. ICT has a lot of things to both teachers and students for the enhancement of their vocabulary and improvement of English language skills. Now-a-days ICT tools and approaches are being used widely due to their convenience, omnipresence, and effectiveness and being their status in the society. The integration of the ICT on the internet with English facilitated the creation of a virtual environment that transformed learning from a traditional passive experience to one of discovery, exploration, and excitement in a less stressful setting.

Language acquisition is an area where open access resources, online courses, virtual classrooms and social networks based on information and communication technology are being increasingly used to give learners access to information, promote interaction and communication. ICT enhance digital literacy skills. However, the rapid development of tools and resources presents both opportunities and challenges. In order to maximize the potential power of ICT in a target language learning, it is a crucial that it is used in the individual needs of the learners. It is also important that the use of ICT is introduced and supported in a sustainable way of learning a language and it is for promote lifelong learning.

The modern age is termed as the era of knowledge explosion. This explosion has become possible due to the progress of Science and Technology. Now ICT is being used in a number of fields like, education, research, aviation, media, health, entertainment, movies and TV programs, games and sports, transportation, industries, fashion designing, textile, agriculture etc. with a single click, we can get exchange a lot of information from the different areas and directions of the world due to the use of ICT. The field of education is not untouched by the ICT. Now we cannot imagine education without the use of information and communication technology. It has made exchange of thoughts, ideas, experiences and feelings very easier with the help of ICT a lot of persons can get education and training simultaneously at low cost. Here the use of computers, Internet, Television, Radio, Projectors, mobile phones, emails, Whatsapp, Face book, online audio and video conferencing as well as new applications has made the teaching and learning process and Training attractive and convenient. It is also helpful in saving time, energy and money. So, we can say the most important and pivotal role in the learning of new la Some of these approaches, facilities and teaching Aids are CAL (Computer Assisted Learning), CALA (Computer Assisted Language Assessment), CALI (Computer Assisted Language Instructions), CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning), MALL (Mobile Assisted Language Learning), TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning), Blogs, wiki, e-mail facility, Digital Library, multimedia, mobile learning, free and open source software and social media, Virtual Classrooms, documentaries, Digital class rooms, Digital storytelling, mobile applications, i-pods, Digital note books, Tablets, smart phones, record audios – videos materials, online spoken tutorials, Digital pronunciation dictionaries etc. These facilities have paved the way of individualized learning and provided freedom of learning anytime. Technological sophistication is a significant and promising force for increasing efficiency in education more so in English language teaching and learning. In the past, most teaching was either verbal communication between teacher and students or written communication from printed materials. These communication channels continue to play important roles in the teaching-learning process even today, all the students are learning from pictures, television, recorded lessons and other media etc.

The Advantages of ICT:

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There is no more doubt that the use of ICT has positive effects on foreign language acquiring. The impact is highly dependent on the way it is used for the following impacts seem to be the most obvious ones when using ICT to support a new language learning. The possibility to adopt easily the teaching aids according to the circumstances, learner's needs and response, ICT allows reacting upon and enables the use of recent news; it offers access to authentic materials on the web. Possibility to combine basic skills like texts and images, and audio and video etc. learners become more interesting with the topics, ICT enables to focus on one specific aspect of the lesson like Pronunciation, vocabulary, stress and intonation marks, parts of speech etc. The advantages of ICT usage in foreign language learning as listed:

- a. **Capacity to control presentation:** It marks the difference between computers and books, books have a fixed presentation, unlike computers, which can combine visual with listening comprehension, text with graphics, models and pictures with original colors of the object or module.
- b. **Novelty and creativity:** a learner can use different materials for each lesson, not like in teaching with texts, where all classes presenting a certain topic are the same.
- c. **Feedback:** computers provide a fast feedback to the learners answers through error correction. It not only spots the mistakes but also correct it, sometimes even giving the appropriate advice.
- d. **Adaptability:** computer programs can be adapted learners to suit their standards, needs and level of the of the learners and subject knowledge.

The Internet and Language Learning:

The internet offers the best way to learn language other than immersion in an English speaking area. The advantages of online learning can be summarized under the following headings:

- a. **Access:** Internet offers the possibility to experience English without the need of travel. Even without the need of leaving home or bedroom.
- b. **Flexibility:** to learn language when they want, where they want.
- c. **Response:** the possibility of instant feedback to the learners. It greatly enhances the learner's experience.
- d. **Repeatability:** the learner can encounter the language in a repetitive fashion until mastery is achieved.

- e. **Durability:** the internet is 24/7 and 365 round the clock. It never tires, it does not take breaks or rest, it never feel bore.
- f. **Modality:** it is a multi model learning tool. It stimulates in a rich sensory and cognitive and thus fertilizes language acquisition successfully.
- g. **Specificity:** the language learner choice and variety in both in what and with who will be learned. Learning can be tailored to the language learners precise make up and needs.
- h. **Cost:** it is a business model which due to economies of scale, can offer service for usage of software. It also offers to widen access through a pay as you can dynamic.
- i. The internet mediated communication allows users to share not only brief messages, but also create lengthy documents, thus facilitating collaborative learning.
- j. Furthermore, the learners can share graphics, sounds and video. Thus, the internet helps create an environment where authentic and creative communication is integrated into all aspects of the course.

A computer-Assisted learning, particularly integrated learning systems, and outcomes with respect to a target language. Some of the important ICT tools and applications used in the field of English language Teaching is following:

1. **Computers:** This is the most important tool of Information and Communication Technology and backbone of modern education system. It is helpful in storing preparing, collecting and preparing of data for communication. It is helpful in the development of L-S-R-W skills. It's very helpful especially Listening and Speaking skills.
2. **Over Head Projectors:** it is an important tool of displaying information and process to a large number of people simultaneously. It can be used in teaching and training of personal. Prepared forms of information, slides, pictures etc are easy to display, convince, understanding and to explain with the help of OHP.
3. **Radio:** it is very useful in the Education and Training for the rural area students. Many courses like Distance and Open Education programs are being conducted with help of Radio. It is also useful in audio conferencing. Programs relayed on radio are helpful in the development of language skills, especially commentaries, storytelling, conversations, dialogues and dramas.
4. **Television:** it is useful in education as well as entertainment of the people. It is found that it is helpful in developing in listening skills, useful learning is situational language as well as it is highly motivating also. It is very helpful in understanding the language of mass

media. A large number of students may be benefited with the programs of television for class lectures, debates, group discussions, seminars, workshops, conferences simultaneously. Many distance and open universities are running their educational programs on television, such as Indira Gandhi National Open University, Maulana Azad National Urdu University, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Open University, T-SAT, Gndarshan, Nipuna etc. it is an important tool of audio visual – video conferencing. Live telecast of training and discussions are done through the television for better learning from home.

5. **Lingua Franca:** this tool is very important in language training of the students. A number of students can practice speaking and hearing drills with the help of lingua phone. It is especially useful in the training of English language listening and speaking skills.
6. **Internet:** it is the most important facility of communication in all the aspects from dawn to dusk. All the modern communication takes place through this. It has made the communication very fast, convenient, accurate, economic, reliable and attractive. There are so many advantages with the internet like.
7. **Social Media:** Social media has become an important tool of communication. It provides a platform for sharing thoughts and ideas. Blogs are made on it. Teachers and Students can add themselves with the English language learning groups and take advantage of sharing information. More and more social sites are available on it like, Watts App, Face book, Twitter, Instagram, Telegram etc. it is helpful in learning the situational language.
8. **E-learning:** online facilities for English language learning. A lot of online facilities are available on internet for the development of language skills. Some of them are e-guidance, e-tutors, e-teaching, e-journals, e-magazines, e-books, e-library, digital libraries, online training courses, virtual classes, e-programs, e-classes, e-reading, etc.
9. **E-courses:** online language related courses are available on internet. Some of them are Free and some of them are Payable. Students can enroll themselves in these courses and get education and training easily on their own place. Students can watch online and off line videos of language learning for the enhancement of their language skills.
10. **Films and Videos:** Films and videos can be used in the teaching of English language. It may be documentaries, videos, lectures, seminars, workshops, conferences, group discussions, debates, conversations, presentations etc educational and entertainment based

programs. These can arouse high level of motivation to the learner. It results in a most satisfying experience of learning. Using short and feature-length videos is an engaging way to work on skills like vocabulary and comprehension. Videos help to expose students to the use of natural English. Young children really enjoy short cartoons and animated movies, and older students can learn about current events through news broadcasts.

11. **Apps:** Apps on smart phones and tablets are great ways for students to practice English and have fun while doing it. For practicing grammar rules, apps like grammar up allow students to test their knowledge on specific topics (verbs, prepositions, etc.).
12. **Digital Field Trips:** Students absorb a great deal of information through experiential learning, but field trips are not always an option with limited school budgets.
 - a. **Podcasts:** Students can listen to podcasts to improve their comprehension. They can also create podcasts to practice their English speaking abilities. There are multiple podcasts tailored specifically for English language learners. Teachers can also have students create podcasts to give them opportunities to practice their speaking skills. With just a microphone and a computer, students can create reports and presentations.
 - b. **Pen Pals:** Since snail mail is becoming a thing of the past, students can have pen pals that they email or write to on a discussion board. Make an arrangement with an English-speaking class in another state or country and have students write to their pen pal on a regular basis. This is a great way for them to practice their English writing and reading comprehension skills,
13. **Web Quests:** Web quests are a fun way for students to use the Internet to build English proficiency. Students are given a task and rely on their content knowledge and grasp of English language to complete it.
14. **Online Games:** Students can master spelling, grammar and other English skills by playing games on the computer or mobile devices. For younger students to increase English literacy skills. Digital versions of hangman, Scrabble and Boggle are also entertaining for all ages of students. Many of these games can be put up on interactive white boards to get full class participation.
15. **Blogging:** Class blogs provide great forums for students to practice their writing skills. One of the reasons that students find blogging appealing is that it is more of an authentic

writing experience, as a wider audience typically has access to read posted entries, which means students tend to put more effort into their blogs.

16. **Skype:** Skype is a great way for students to practice their speaking and listening skills with other people from any location. Students can have question-and-answer sessions with authors of books, attend video-conferences and virtual field trips, interview professionals, and connect with students from other cultures and countries. Skype can even be used to conduct parent-teacher conferences or connect with students' family members who may be abroad.
17. **Judge and Jury:** Show two video clips that have opposite view points. For example, you might show one that argues for creationism and the other for evolution, or any debatable topic. Have students write down the arguments for each side as they watch. They should then work in smaller groups to decide which arguments are most important and finally, come to a conclusion based on the points presented in the videos. They can debate between themselves and come up with a unanimous decision.
18. **Quiz Time:** Prepare some questions ahead of time and let the students know that they should pay careful attention to the dialogue while they are watching the video. Once it is over, ask them the questions. If the students have trouble with the questions, watch the clip again so they can find the answers, rather than simply telling them. It's a good way to practice listening with them.
19. **Create a Storyboard:** Watch a fairly short video that has some different action and plenty of dialogue. The video should have several distinct parts that will be easy to map on a storyboard. Allow students to watch the whole thing while taking notes, then go back and watch each segment. Pause between segments so students can draw the scene and note what happens between the characters. Another option is to make the storyboard on the whiteboard at the front of the class, calling on students to tell you what should be included. They can take their own notes and then help you design the actual storyboard.
20. **Pick a Character:** Have each student choose a character to pay particular attention to. They should observe everything from how the person reacts to various situations to how they speak and how emotional they are. After the video, have students write down diary entries for their chosen character.

CONCLUSION:

In the domain of language acquisition, open access resources are utilised. ICT provides students with an effective learning environment. ICT is regarded as an effective tool for educational practice in any discipline; it can be seamlessly incorporated into the learning process, provided that instructors provide learners with extensive training and knowledge. By establishing and maintaining communication and a connection through the use of ICT, we can inform them of our support with a single click, while simultaneously granting them the autonomy to focus on the aspects of their education that are most significant to them. Additionally, these tools facilitate self-preparation and foster genuine communication in a setting where such input is scarce, while also offering the advantage of being convenient and time-efficient. As the intersection of ICT and language learning draws to a close, the discourse shifts from language use to language learning itself, emphasizing how the characteristics of language learning have evolved in tandem with technological progress, potentially in response to its facilitation of effortless acquisition and comprehension of the target language. As with any other human endeavor, language learning is susceptible to the impact of social developments and trends. Examining technological aspects of language evolution can contribute to a more comprehensive comprehension of the challenges faced in applied linguistics, thus influencing the trajectory of future developments. It enables the identification of trends and patterns and reveals pertinent insights regarding the present circumstances and ongoing discussions. However, the majority of them are conventional, uninteresting, ineffective, and devoid of motivation. As a result, it is imperative that contemporary approaches and ICT tools be utilised to facilitate the acquisition and comprehension of English language fundamentals such as L-S-R-W by students of all levels and members of society. ICT offers numerous benefits to educators and learners alike, including the ability to expand one's vocabulary and improve proficiency in the English language. Present-day ICT tools and methods are extensively utilised on account of their efficacy, pervasiveness, and convenience, as well as their social standing.

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